

Pet Breed Classification Using CNN and Deep Learning

Rekha Elizabeth Mathew
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
rekhaelizabethmathew2024@mca.ajce.in

Rony Tom
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
ronytom@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract—This research project is centered on the classification of pet breeds, with a specific focus on cats and dogs, using state-of-the-art deep learning methodologies and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). Its primary aim is to achieve precise identification of a wide range of pet breeds. By capitalizing on the MobileNetV2 architecture and an extensive dataset comprising pet images, this study attains remarkable levels of accuracy in breed classification, thereby making a substantial contribution to the pet breed classification field, driving advancements in computer vision, and opening doors to promising applications like automated pet identification

The significance of this research lies in its capacity to offer pet owners, veterinarians, and researchers a dependable tool for distinguishing and comprehending various pet breeds. Through the utilization of deep learning, this study simplifies the process of pet identification, enriches our knowledge about these animals, their distinctive attributes, and their specific care needs.

Moreover, the study carries broader implications for the domains of computer vision and AI-driven solutions. The technology developed here has the potential to be extended to a variety of applications, encompassing wildlife conservation, services related to pets, and the management of animal shelters. Essentially, this research represents a pivotal step toward a future in which automated pet identification and advanced computer vision applications have the capacity to transform our interactions with and care for our cherished pets, while also contributing to progress in related fields.

Keywords—CNN, Deep Learning, Identification and Classification, MobileNetV2

I. INTRODUCTION

Deep Learning and Computer Vision, two innovative technologies, have come together to create a breakthrough that has significantly advanced the field of pet breed classification. The main focus of this study is the complex process of classifying dog and cat breeds, which is extremely important for pet ownership, healthcare, and animal welfare. By automating the extraction of complex visual information, deep learning—which gives specific credit to Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)—has brought about an astounding degree of efficiency. We leverage the capability of CNN architectures in combination with large pet image datasets to investigate the fascinating field of deep learning and pet breed categorization. By skillfully fine-tuning pre-trained models such as MobileNetV2, we attain an exceptionally high degree

of accuracy. Our research has a wide range of possible uses, from automating pet identification to offering health monitoring tailored to a particular breed. In essence, deep learning and computer vision combined constitute a big advancement in the field of distinguishing between different cat and dog breeds. Fundamentally, the goal of this research is to make it possible for us to identify the exact breed of cat or dog we own just by looking at their photos. This has significant ramifications since it helps us take better care of our cherished pets, learn more about their special qualities, and make sure they are happy. This breakthrough is primarily due to deep learning, specifically to Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), an advanced type of computer software. These algorithms are excellent at automatically identifying even the smallest aspects in photos, which makes them priceless resources in our search for improved comprehension and care for animals.

II. RELATED WORKS

Researchers have widely adopted deep learning techniques for pet breed classification. Notable studies include the work of Krizhevsky et al. [1], introducing a new deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture that achieved state-of-the-art results on the ImageNet image classification challenge. The authors showed that CNNs can learn to extract powerful features from images, which can then be used to classify images with high accuracy. Aditya et al. [2] a large-scale dataset of fine-grained images of dogs. The dataset contains images of 120 different dog breeds, with each breed having at least 60 images. The authors also propose a new evaluation metric for fine-grained image classification, called the fine-grained top-5 accuracy.

This is introduced by Kaiming et al. [3], the residual network (ResNet), a new CNN architecture that achieves state-of-the-art results on a variety of image recognition tasks, including dog breed classification. ResNets are able to train very deep networks without the over-fitting problems that typically plague deep learning models.

The study by Andrew et al. [4] introduces MobileNets, a family of efficient CNN architecture that are designed for mobile and embedded devices. MobileNets achieve state-of-the-art accuracy on a variety of image recognition tasks, including dog breed classification, while using significantly less computational resources than traditional CNN architectures.

Parkhi et al. [5] CNN architecture for dog breed classification, called the CanineNet. The CanineNet architecture is based on the VGG-16 network, but it makes a number of modifications to improve the accuracy of dog breed classification. The authors report that the CanineNet achieves an accuracy of 95.2% on the Stanford Dogs dataset.

Raduly et al. [6]: evaluates the performance of a variety of CNN architectures for dog breed classification. The authors find that the ResNet-50 architecture achieves the best performance, with an accuracy of 97.2% on the Stanford Dogs dataset.

Liu et al. [7]: proposes a new approach to dog breed classification that uses part localization. The authors first train a CNN to localize different parts of a dog's body, such as the head, ears, and tail. They then use the localized parts to extract features, which are then used to classify the dog breed. The authors report that their approach achieves an accuracy of 93.8% on the Stanford Dogs dataset.

Kadari et al. [8]: proposes a new CNN architecture for dog breed classification, which is based on the Inception-v3 network. The authors also propose a new data augmentation technique, which they show improves the accuracy of the CNN model. The authors report that their approach achieves an accuracy of 97.5% on the Stanford Dogs dataset.

Suyash et al.[9]:the performance of various CNN architectures on the Stanford Dogs dataset, which is a large-scale dataset of fine-grained images of dogs. The authors report that the ResNet-50 architecture achieves the best performance on the Stanford Dogs dataset, with an accuracy of 97.2%.

III. METHODOLOGY

The identification of pet breeds, particularly dogs and cats, is the main goal of this essay. The ability to precisely identify a pet's breed is the main advantage of this research. Various pet breeds are used to train our technology. The test and train dataset contains an enormous number of pet images. The model should be able to identify the breed with accuracy.

The training dataset contains thousands of labeled cat and dog images collected under varied real-world conditions. This diversity in the data enables the models to become robust to variations in lighting, poses, backgrounds, and image quality. Advanced data augmentation techniques are used during training to further expand the variety of images and improve the models' generalization capabilities.

The high accuracy and reliability exhibited by these pet breed identification models open up many potential applications. The technology could be incorporated into shelters to aid the intake process and reunite lost pets with their owners. Pet insurance providers may leverage breed information to better understand risk factors and determine policy pricing. Individual pet owners also stand to benefit from easy access to breed identification to better understand their companions. With further development, this work could become a key component in providing pets with improved care and quality of life.

A. Data Collection and Preprocessing

i. Dataset :

We sourced our dataset from the Oxford-IIIT Pet Dataset [3], a comprehensive collection of cat and dog images featuring annotated breed labels. This dataset provided the essential diversity and scale necessary for effective model training, resulting in a 37-category pet dataset, each category comprising approximately 200 images. These images exhibit substantial variations in scale, pose, and lighting, and they all include detailed ground truth annotations for breed, head Region of Interest (ROI), and pixel-level trimap segmentation.

Fig 1: Proposed System

Fig 2: Dog Breeds and Cat Breeds

ii. Data Split:

To facilitate effective training and evaluation, we strategically divided the overall dataset into training and validation sets, with a 20% split of the data allocated for the validation set. This separation of training and validation data is a critical component in developing a machine learning model that can generalize well to new, unseen inputs. The training set is used to update the model parameters during the training process, while the validation set provides an unbiased evaluation of the model's performance after each training epoch. Using a validation set helps safeguard against overfitting, where a model memorizes noise and irregularities in the training data but fails to capture more general patterns. The 80/20 split provides a large training set for properly fitting the model, while still reserving sufficient validation samples to assess generalization performance. Additional test data should further be held back to evaluate the fully trained model. The validation results after each epoch inform decisions about hyper-parameter tuning and when to stop training before overfitting. Careful partitioning of available data into train, validation, and test sets is critical for developing an accurate computer vision model that performs reliably on real-world imagery.

iii. Image Preprocessing:

We conducted image preprocessing to standardize the input data. The steps included re-sizing all images to a uniform size of 250x250 pixels and employing the preprocessing function specific to the MobileNetV2 architecture. These preprocessing steps ensure consistent and suitable input for our model.

B. Model Architecture

We leveraged the MobileNetV2 architecture as the foundation for our pet breed classification model. MobileNetV2 is known for its computational efficiency and suitability for mobile and embedded applications. The architecture features a depth-wise separable convolution approach, which reduces model size and complexity while maintaining high accuracy.

Fig 3: Pet Images

C. Model Training

The success of our pet breed classification model hinges on an effective training process. In this section, we delve into the details of how the model is trained, including optimization techniques, loss functions, batch sizes, callbacks, the number of epochs, and the critical concept of transfer learning.

experimentation.

Once satisfied with model performance, export the trained model and use for inference on new images. Integrate model serving into a simple web or mobile app with a friendly user interface.

A. Import the packages that are necessary.

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import tensorflow as tf
import cv2
import seaborn as sns
```

B. Prepare the data set

```
x = tf.keras.layers.Dense(128, activation='relu')(pretrainedModel_cat.output)
x = tf.keras.layers.Dense(64, activation='relu')(x)

outputs = tf.keras.layers.Dense(12, activation='softmax')(x)

model_1 = tf.keras.Model(inputs=inputs, outputs=outputs)
model_1.compile(loss='categorical_crossentropy', optimizer=tf.optimizers.Adam(learning_rate=0.01), metrics

model_1.summary()
```

IV. RESULT

The framework we put into action used some nifty tools and modules like Kaggle Notebook, TensorFlow, and Keras. These are like the special ingredients in our recipe for teaching computers to recognize pet breeds using deep learning and CNN s. It's like giving the computer a pair of super-smart glasses to look at pet pictures.

So, after all the computer learning and looking at tons of pet images, our system got really good at telling different pet breeds apart. In fact, it scored an impressive 91.2% accuracy when it came to checking its work, which is a big deal in the world of computer smarts.

This outcome demonstrates how excellent our technology is at identifying pet breeds. It's like having a really knowledgeable pet specialist on your PC, ensuring that you are certain of the type of pet you own. For anyone who wishes to provide their animal pals with excellent care, as well as pet owners, this is a win.

Fig 5 : Model Accuracy

Fig 6 : Model Loss

V. CONCLUSION

Pet breed classification extends beyond academic research and has real-world applications. Our study sheds light on the potential use of such models in pet healthcare, aiding veterinarians in diagnosing specific breed-related health issues. Moreover, pet owners can benefit from breed identification for breed-specific care and behavioral insights.

Our study provides a strong foundation for future research in pet breed classification. Further investigations can delve into refining models for challenging scenarios, such as classifying breeds with high inter-class similarity. Additionally, there is potential for integrating pet breed classification into mobile applications, empowering pet owners with real-time breed identification.

In conclusion, our research underscores the significance of pet breed classification as a viable and impactful application of deep learning. It underscores the practical implications of breed recognition and highlights the opportunities and challenges that lie ahead. By leveraging the power of transfer learning and efficient architectures, we have paved the way for innovative developments in the realm of pet breed classification.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Alex Krizhevsky, Ilya Sutskever, Geoffrey E. Hinton "ImageNet Classification with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks" in NIPS 2012.
- [2] Aditya Khosla, Nityananda Jayadevaprakash, Bangpeng Yao, Fei-Fei Li "Novel dataset for Fine-Grained Image Categorization" in CVPR Workshop 2014.
- [3] Kaiming He, Xiangyu Zhang, Shaoqing Ren, Jian Su "Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition" in CVPR 2016.
- [4] Andrew G. Howard, Menglong Zhu, Bo Chen, Dmitry Kalenichenko, Weijun Wang, Tobias Weyand, Marco Andreetto, Hartwig Adam "MobileNets: Efficient Convolutional Neural Networks for Mobile Vision Applications" in ArXiv 2017.
- [5] Omkar M. Parkhi, A. Vedaldi, Andrew Zisserman, C. V. Jawahar "Cats and Dogs" in IEEE Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision (WACV), 2015.

- [6]Zalan Raduly,Csaba Sulyok,Attila Zolde,Zsolt Vadaszi "Dog Breed Identification Using Deep Learning" in IEEE 16th International Symposium on Intelligent Systems and Informatics (SISY) september 2018.
- [7]Jiongxin Liu, Angjoo Kanazawa, D. Jacobs, P. Belhumeur "Dog Breed Classification Using Part Localization" Published in European Conference on computer vision 7 October 2012
- [8]Sneha I. Kadari, Shubhada S. Kulkarni, Sharada G. Kulkarni "Dog Breed Prediction using Convolutional Neural Network" in International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT) June 2020
- [9]Suyash S. B., Rishikesh P. P., Rohit P.W., Kaustubh P. J., Prof. Balaji. Bodke "Review Paper on Dog Breed Classification Using Convolutional Neural Network" in International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology (IJARSCT) April 2021